

Why Green Marketing is Essential for our Environment

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Abstract:- "Green marketing is a phenomenon that has gained a lot of traction in the current market. This approach has made it possible to re-market and package existing items that already follow these rules. Furthermore, the growth of green marketing has created new opportunities. Enabling corporations to co-brand their products into various lines, praising some for their environmental friendliness while dismissing others neglecting the opinions of others as will be described, such marketing strategies are a direct outcome of mobility. In the minds of the general public as a result, companies have boosted their targeting rate. Customers who are environmentally conscious. These same customers are interested in incorporating environmental concerns into their purchase decisions through the method and content of the marketing strategy for whatever product is necessary, as a result of their concern. This article examines how firms have expanded their focus on green consumers, or individuals who care about the environment and let it influence their purchase habits. The report outlines three distinct groups of green customers and examines the problems and possibilities that green marketing presents for firms. The article also looks at the current trends in green marketing in India, as well as the reasons why firms are embracing it and the future of green marketing, concluding that green marketing will continue to expand in popularity and practice.

Keywords:- Green Product, Recyclable, environmentally safe, Eco Friendly.

I. INTRODUCTION

Green marketing, according to the American Marketing Association, is the promotion of items that are assumed to be ecologically friendly. As a result, green marketing encompasses a wide variety of actions, including product modification, modifications to the manufacturing process, packaging improvements, and advertising adjustments. However, defining green marketing is a difficult process since numerous meanings overlap and contradict one another; one example is the existence of several social, environmental, and retail connotations for this phrase. Environmental marketing and ecological marketing are two more phrases that are used interchangeably. As a result, "green marketing" refers to a holistic marketing concept in which products and services are produced, distributed, consumed, and disposed of in a manner that is less harmful to the environment. As consumers and marketers become more aware of the effects of global warming, non biodegradable solid waste, and the harmful effects of pollutants, for example, both marketers and consumers are becoming more sensitive to the need to

switch to green products and services. While the transition to "green" may appear to be costly in the near term, it will undoubtedly prove vital and cost-effective in the long run.

II. WHY GREEN MARKETING?

It's terrifying to read the following excerpts from a recent article in the New York Times: "People, farms, and animals in the United States have been harmed by air contamination. Each year, tens of billions of dollars are spent"" More than a dozen additional studies in the United States, Brazil, Europe, Mexico, South Korea, and Taiwan have found correlations between air pollution and low birth weight, still birth, and infant mortality."

It is crucial for marketers to make the best use of available resources while still reaching the organization's objectives since resources are scarce and human demands are insatiable. Green marketing is therefore unavoidable. Environmental protection is a growing issue for consumers everywhere in the world. There is evidence that people are concerned about the environment and are changing their behaviors all around the world. Green marketing, which describes the expanding market for products and services that are both ecologically and socially responsible, has developed as a result.

People want to leave a clean earth to their successors as a result of consumers' growing awareness of the value of safeguarding the environment in which they live. Numerous surveys carried out by environmentalists reveal that people are concerned about the environment and are changing their behavior to be more environmentally friendly. We can see that most clients, whether individual and corporate, are becoming more and more interested about buying ecologically friendly products.

The majority of them think it is safe to use ecologically friendly products. As a result, green marketing has emerged with the intention of promoting goods and services that are both environmentally friendly and morally upright. We are now living in the era of recyclable, non-toxic, and ecologically friendly products. Marketers that want to satisfy client needs while boosting profits now live by this new adage.

In order to satisfy the expectations of customers who desire high-quality, high-performance, and convenient products at a fair price that do not harm the environment, green marketing involves developing and promoting goods and services. In order to lessen the negative effects of products, their use, and their disposal on the environment, it encompasses a wide range of actions such as product modification, production process changes, updated

advertising, packaging changes, and so on. Globally, businesses strive to reduce the impact of their goods and services on the environment, including the climate and other variables. Marketers are embracing green and following suit.

Following the proceedings of the first workshop on ecological marketing conducted in Austin, Texas (US) in 1975, green marketing gained traction in the late 1980s and 1990s. Following then, more books on green marketing were produced. Green marketing confronts several obstacles, according to Joel Makeover (a writer, lecturer, and strategist on clean technology and green marketing), because to a lack of standards and public consensus on what defines "green."

The concept of green marketing has developed throughout time.

Green marketing has gone through three stages, according to Peattie (2001). All marketing activities during the first phase, which was known as "Ecological" green marketing, were concentrated on assisting with environmental problems and offering solutions. The second stage was "Environmental" green marketing, when the focus shifted to clean technology and the creation of novel new goods to address problems with waste and pollution. The third phase was the "Sustainable" green marketing phase. It got famous in the late 1990s and early 2000s.

The holistic marketing idea includes green marketing as an important component. It is especially relevant for enterprises that are directly dependent on the physical environment, such as fishing, processed foods, tourism, and adventure sports.

Changes in the physical environment might put such industries at risk. Green marketing methods are currently

being effectively implemented by several worldwide companies in a variety of industries.

A. The three R's of environmentalism are:

- Reduce
- Reuse and,
- Recycle

B. Green Products and its Characteristics:

Green products are those that are made using environmentally friendly technologies and do not harm the environment. Green technologies and green goods must be promoted in order to conserve natural resources and achieve long-term growth. The following criteria can be used to define green products:

- Products those are originally grown,
- Products those are recyclable, reusable and biodegradable,
- Products with natural ingredients,
- Products containing recycled contents, non-toxic chemical,
- Products contents under approved chemical,
- Products that do not harm or pollute the environment,
- Products that will not be tested on animals,
- Products that have eco-friendly packaging i.e., reusable, refillable containers etc.

C. Goals of Green Marketing

- Eliminate the concept of waste.
- Reinvent the concept of product.
- Make prices reflect actual and environmental costs.
- Make environmentalism profitable.
- Bringing out product modifications.
- Changing in production processes.
- Packaging changes.
- Modifying advertising.

Need of Green Marketing: An Anthropological View

Major dangers to human health include ozone layer loss and global warming. Everyone wants to live a good life that is full of health and vigor, whether they are wealthy or poor or members of the corporate elite. Every corporate entity has as its primary objective generating revenue and profit. The environmental cost of conducting business as usual throughout the globe is, however, slowly but surely, becoming more and more understood. This perception is encouraging corporate citizenship in the business sector. Therefore, long-term sustainable business, customer happiness, and receiving a sanction license from the regulatory body continue to drive the business class's motivation for green marketing. Industries in Asian countries are catching the need of green marketing from the developed countries but still there is a wide gap between their understanding and implementation.

III. CHALLENGES IN GREEN MARKETING

A. Need for Standardization

Only 5% of the marketing messages produced by HGreenI are entirely true, and there are no standards in place to back up these assertions.

There are no established criteria to support these claims. A standard for certifying a product as organic is not yet in existence. Unless certain regulatory authorities are engaged in granting the certifications, there won't be any means that can be verified. A typical quality control board is necessary for this labelling and licensing.

B. New Concept

The educated and urban customers of India are becoming increasingly aware of the advantages of green products. However, it is still a fresh idea to the general population. Environmental risks need to be explained to and made clear to the client. The majority will need to be reached by the new green movements, which will take time and effort. Because of their ayurvedic heritage, Indian clients understand the significance of using natural and herbal beauty products. Yoga and the use of natural foods are

prominent healthy living practices in India. Customers are more inclined to accept green products since they are already aware of these problems.

C. Patience and Perseverance

Investors, companies, and marketers must see the environment as a tremendous long-term investment opportunity and take into account the long-term advantages of this new green movement. There won't be any immediate results, and it will require a lot of patience. It will take some time for people to embrace it because it is a new concept and thought.

D. Avoiding Green Myopia

The fundamental principle of green marketing is to focus on customer benefits, or the main reason why consumers purchase certain products. If you succeed, you may convince clients to switch products or even pay more for the environmentally friendly choice. It won't help if a product is created that is entirely green in every manner but falls short of the requirements for customer happiness. There will be green myopia as a result of this. Additionally, if green products are priced too much, they could not find a market.

Benefits of Green Marketing

Consumers nowadays are growing more socially conscious and ecologically conscious. Because of this, more companies are catering to consumer expectations for environmentally friendly or neutral products. Many companies want to enter the market first because they understand that becoming green will eventually be necessary. The advantages of green marketing include the following:

- It assures long-term development and profitability while also saving money in the long run, despite the higher initial cost.
- It assists businesses in marketing their products and services while keeping environmental concerns in mind.

It assists in gaining access to new markets and gaining a competitive advantage. The majority of employees are also proud and obligated to work for an ecologically conscious organization.

IV. GOLDEN RULES OF GREEN MARKETING

- **Know Your Customer:** Ensure that the consumer is aware of and concerned about the problems that your product is attempting to solve. (Whirlpool discovered the hard way that consumers are fickle. I wouldn't pay a higher price for a CFC-free product. Customers don't know what's in the fridge because they don't know what's in CFCs were one of them.)
- **Educating Your Customer:** It's not simply an issue of informing people that you're doing your part to safeguard the environment; it's also a matter of explaining why it matters. Otherwise, a large chunk of your target market would think, "So what?" and your green marketing effort will fail.
- **Being Genuine and Transparent:** indicates that a) you're doing what you say you're doing in your green marketing strategy, and b) the rest of your business practices are in line with whatever environmentally friendly activities you're undertaking. Both of these requirements must be accomplished in order for your company to build the type

of environmental credentials that will allow a green marketing strategy to thrive.

- **Reassure the Buyer:** Consumers must be convinced that the product does what it is meant to accomplish; they will not sacrifice product quality for the sake of the environment.
- **Consider Your Pricing:** If you're going to charge a premium for your product—which many ecologically preferred items do because of economies of scale and the use of higher-quality ingredients—make sure that those customers can afford it and believe it's worth it.
- **Giving Your Customer an Opportunity to Participate:** implies tailoring the advantages of your environmentally beneficial efforts to the individual client, usually by allowing them to participate in positive environmental action.
- **Thus, leading brands should recognize that consumer expectations have changed:** It is not enough for a corporation to green its products; customers expect the things they buy to be affordable as well as assist them decrease their own environmental effect.

Green Marketing - Adopts by the Farms

It is insufficient for a corporation to become green with its production. Green marketing has been widely adopted by businesses all over the world, and the following are some of the reasons for this widespread adoption:

- ✓ **Opportunities:** As consumer preferences shift, many companies see this as a chance to capitalize on and gain a competitive edge over companies selling non-environmentally friendly alternatives. Some examples of companies that have made strenuous efforts to become more environmentally responsible in order to better meet their customers' requirements include:

- McDonald's replaced its clam shell packaging with waxed paper because of increased consumer concern relating to polystyrene production and Ozone depletion.
- Tuna manufacturers modified their fishing techniques because of the increased concern over driftnet fishing, and the resulting death of dolphins.
- Xerox introduced a "high quality" recycled photocopier paper in an attempt to satisfy the demands of firms for less environmentally harmful products.

- **Governmental Pressure:** Governments seek to "protect" customers and society, as they do with other marketing-related activities; this protection has important green marketing consequences. Environmental marketing restrictions are intended to safeguard consumers in numerous ways, according to BVIMR Management Edge, Vol. 7, No. 1 (2014) PP 78-86 81 government regulations.
 - Reduce the amount of damaging goods or byproducts produced. Reduce the usage and/or consumption of hazardous items by consumers and business.
 - Ensure that all sorts of customers are able to assess the environmental impact of products. Governments enact

restrictions to limit the quantity of hazardous waste created by businesses.

Until the Supreme Court of India ordered a fuel shift, New Delhi, the capital of India, was polluting quickly. A directive was issued in 2002 requiring the use of CNG in all public transportation systems in an effort to minimize pollution. One of the more recent reported environmental laws passed by nations is the creation of regulations to "control" green marketing claims. They include the "Environmental Claims in Marketing - A Guideline" from the Australian Trade Practices Commission (TPC), the "Guides for the Use of Environmental Marketing Claims"

from the US Federal Trade Commission (FTC), and the suggested guidelines from the National Association of Attorneys-General (NAAG). All of these rules attempt to provide customers the knowledge they need to assess the veracity of environmental claims made by businesses.

- Competitive Pressure:** Another significant factor in environmental marketing has been businesses' desire to maintain their competitive edge. Businesses frequently take note of competitors' ads. Imitate environmental behavior as much as possible. This intense competitive pressure, which may be debilitating in some situations, has driven a whole sector to adapt and, as a result, reduced the business's environmentally destructive behavior. For One example of a claim would be Xerox's HReVive. The book "100% Recycled Paper" was published a few years ago. as a defense against the spread of recyclable materials. In another instance, for instance, when one tuna producer stopped using, other manufacturers' photocopier paper, other driftnets followed suit.

- Social Responsibility:** Many companies are becoming aware of their ties to the greater community and the need to behave sustainably as a result. This relates to companies who believe they must accomplish both environmental and financial objectives. Environmental difficulties therefore become a part of the corporate culture of the organisation. Both strategies are used by businesses, according to records. When making investments, fund managers and business developers also take the company's environmental sustainability into account. Venture investors are drawn to green enterprises because they perceive potential for development in them. The UK-based HSBC became the first bank in the world to become carbon neutral in late this year, and it is currently turning its 11000 facilities in 76 different countries into energy efficiency models. Our customers have told us that they decide where they shop based on whether the business is a good neighbor "says David North, Tesco's community director.

Coca-Cola is an illustration of a business that doesn't promote its environmental initiatives. To lessen their impact on the environment, they have modified their packaging and spent a lot of money on recycling. Despite caring about the environment, Coke has not used

environmental issues as a marketing strategy. As a result, it's possible that many customers are uninformed of Coke's commitment to the environment. Another business that is very environmentally responsible is Walt Disney World, although it doesn't advertise this, at least not outside the firm (WDW). WDW has a strong garbage management infrastructure and programmed on place, albeit these characteristics aren't as heavily highlighted in their regular visitor marketing campaigns.

- Cost of Profit Issues:** Green marketing may also be used by businesses to solve cost or profit challenges. Environmentally damaging by-products, such as polychlorinated biphenyl (PCB) polluted oil, are growing more expensive and difficult to dispose of. As a result, companies that can eliminate dangerous wastes might save a lot of money.

In an effort to cut waste, businesses are regularly obliged to review their production processes. In these circumstances, they typically develop more effective production processes that decrease waste while using fewer specific raw materials. Due to the elimination of waste and raw resources, costs are reduced twice. In other cases, businesses look for end-of-pipe solutions rather than removing garbage. When one company's trash becomes another company's manufacturing input, businesses seek for markets or uses for their waste products. An example of this is a business in Australia that produces acidic waste water as a by-product of production and sells it to a business that neutralizes base materials.

- Some Cases**
 Interestingly, green marketing continues to be an issue of global interest. In fact, Google Trends reports5many companies are adopting green for capturing market opportunity of green marketing in some casesthat, on a relative basis, more searches for Green marketing originated from India than from any other country.

• Countries Promotes Green Marketing

RANK	COUNTRY
1	INDIA
2	UK
3	US
4	THAILAND
5	AUSTRALIA
6	CANADA
7	CHINA

EXAMPLE 1: Best Green IT Project: State Bank of India: Green IT@SBI

By using eco-friendly equipment in its 10,000 new ATMs, the financial behemoth not only saved money and earned carbon credits, but it also set a positive example for other businesses to follow. The Green Channel Counter green service now includes SBI as well. Paperless banking, which does away with the need for deposit slips, withdrawal forms, checks, and financial transactions, is one of the many services that SBI provides. SBI ATM and shopping cards are used to conduct each of these transactions.

State Bank of India turns to wind energy to reduce emissions:

The State Bank of India became the first bank in India to use wind energy with a 15-megawatt wind farm built by Suzlon Energy. There are ten 1.5 MW Suzlon wind turbines in the Coimbatore wind farm. The wind farm spans three states, including 1.5 MW in Gujarat, 4.5 MW in Tamil Nadu, and 9 MW in Maharashtra. The State Bank of India's green banking effort, which aims to lessen the bank's carbon footprint and encourage energy-efficient behavior among its clients, is in its first stages, with the wind project serving as its focal point.

V. BEST GREEN IT PROJECT**• Company Scenario Before Deployment**

Wastage of energy due to usage of CRTs, conventional lighting, and air conditioning in ATMs.

• After Deployment

48508500 KWH of electricity savings, translating to Rs. 24 Cr+ savings in energy bills.

• What was deployed?

- Usage of LCD, LEDs inside ATM and even for signage, and usage of energy efficient ACs.
- Aluminum composite panels were put to use instead of wood-based materials in the preparation of sites.
- 10,000 eco-friendly ATMs across India.

• EXAMPLE 2: GM to launch Spark Electra in India in 2010

Next year, India will see the debut of the Spark Elantra, a new electrified version of the Spark. GM forged a technology alliance with Bangalore-based Reva Electric Car Company last month in order to produce eco-friendly cars for the Indian market. While Reva will provide the technology, GM will handle the engineering and production of the green vehicles.

• EXAMPLE 3: Indian Oil's Green Agenda Green Initiatives

- In April 1996, low Sulphur (0.5 percent) diesel was introduced in metros.
- Extra-low Sulphur (0.25 percent) diesel was introduced in September 1996 in the environmentally fragile Taj Trapezium area, in Delhi in October 1997, and across the country on January 1, 2000.

- In 2001, metros began using diesel with a 0.05 percent Sulphur level.
- Since February 1, 2000, unleaded motor spirit (petrol or gasoline) has been accessible nationwide.
- Green fuels (petrol and diesel) that meet Euro-III emission standards have already been adopted in 13 cities/states, with BS-II fuels being used in the remainder of the country.
- Indian Oil is on track to deliver EURO-III compliant fuels to all regions of the nation by the year 2010, with key cities upgrading to Euro-IV compliant fuels by that time.
- Indian Oil has invested around Rs. 7,000 crores in green fuel projects at its refineries so far, with another Rs. 5,000 crores in the pipeline.
- At the Mathura Refinery, a Motor Spirit Quality Improvement Unit was inaugurated; similar units will be installed at three other refineries.
- All seven Indian oil refineries have diesel quality enhancement facilities in place, and numerous additional green fuel projects are in the works or on the drawing board.
- Indian Oil's research and development Centre is working on eco-friendly biodegradable lubricant compositions.
- The Centre has been certified under ISO14000:1996 for environment management systems.

• Green Fuel Alternatives

In the country's pursuit of alternative sources of energy, Indian Oil is focusing on CNG (compressed natural gas), Auto gas (LPG), ethanol blended petrol, bio-diesel, and Hydrogen energy.

EXAMPLE 4: ITC paper division capacity addition, tech infusion on course.

He mentioned that, while having less brilliance, the 1.3 lakh tonne pulp plant will be able to produce TCF (completely chlorine free) pulp. He said that the brand's new, high-end recycled board version, called "Ecoviron," was used to make its own "Classmate" notebook, which has grown in popularity among students. (The notebooks and Expressions greeting cards are both made in Chennai by the Greeting, Gifting and Stationery Business (GGSB) Division.) According to Mr. Chand Das, the division's CEO, the Classmate Notebooks have risen to the top of the market (Business Daily from THE HINDU group of newspapers). "As more capacity comes on-stream at Bhadrachalam," the statement reads, "we are well placed to extend boundaries throughout the whole spectrum of stationery."

EXAMPLE 5: DELL India

Dell has launched two new efforts in India to encourage people to take a green approach to technology adoption: discount coupons and the Dell Go Green Challenge. Dell's aim to make "going green" simple and cost-effective for consumers continues with these efforts.

• EXAMPLE 6: - Guide to Greener Electronics

The list rates the top 18 computer, mobile phone, television, and video game makers based on their policies on harmful chemicals, recycling, and climate change. May 2010 was the most recent update. This guide's three objectives are to help businesses:

- **Cleanup their Products** by eliminating hazardous substance.
- **Take back & Recycle** products responsibly once they become obsolete.
- **Reduce the climate Impact** of their operations and products.

In which: **Nokia in 1st Position with 7.5**

Nokia maintains its lead with a score of 7.5, up from 7.3 before. It earns points for meeting its target of

eliminating brominated substances, chlorinated flame retardants, and antimony trioxide from all new product models by 2020, as well as its CEO's support for a 30 percent reduction in greenhouse gas emissions in developed nations by 2020.

Despite its support for additional legislation restricting chlorinated and brominated substances, Nokia loses a point on the RoHS (Restriction of Hazardous Substances in Electronics) Directive because it does not openly support restrictions on PVC vinyl plastic, chlorinated flame retardants (CFRs), and brominated flame retardants (BFRs) in the next 3-5 years.

Sony Ericsson is 2nd with 6.9

Other Companies are as follows:

3rd - Philips 5.1	7th – Sony4.9	11th - Acer 4.1	15th – Fujitsu3.5
4th – Motorola5.1	8th – HP4.9	12th - LG Electronics3.7	16th - Microsoft 3.3
5th - Apple 4.9	9th – Sharp4.5	13th - Samsung 3.7	17th - Lenovo 1.9
6th - Panasonic 4.9	10th – Dell4.3	14th - Toshiba 3.5	18th – Nintendo1.8

VI. PRESENT TRENDS IN GREEN MARKETING IN INDIA

• Organizations are Perceive Environmental marketing as an Opportunity to achieve its objectives. Consumers choose items that do not impair the natural environment or human health, according to businesses. Firms that promote such green products are chosen over those that do not, gaining a competitive edge while also satisfying their commercial objectives.

• Organizations believe they have a moral obligation to be more socially responsible.

This is consistent with the CSR principle, which has been effectively implemented by many businesses to improve their public image. In this case, companies may adopt one of two approaches: use their environmental stewardship as a marketing weapon.

Become responsible without being prompted to do so.

- **Governmental Bodies are forcing Firms to Become More Responsible.** In most circumstances, the government requires the company to implement policies that safeguard customers' interests. It accomplishes so by reducing the creation of hazardous items or by-products in the following ways:
 - Ensure that all types of consumers have the ability to analyze the environmental composition of items; or
 - Modify consumer and industrial usage and/or consumption of damaging goods.
- **Competitors' Environmental Activities Pressure Firms to Change their Environmental Marketing Activities.**

Firms switch to green marketing in order to counter competitors' claims of being environmentally friendly. As a result, green marketing has spread throughout the sector.

- **Cost Factors Associated with Waste Disposal or Reductions in Material Usage Forces Firms to Modify their Behavior.** As cost reducing becomes a component of a company's strategy, it embraces green marketing in regard to the environment. Certain kinds of activity it may pursue these as follows:
 - A company creates a technology for lowering costs
 - It recycles garbage and sells it to other businesses.

The Future of Green Marketing

The short version is that effective green marketing requires the use of strong marketing principles in order to make green products appealing to buyers. There are various lessons to be learned in order to avoid green marketing myopia. What is the future of green marketing, meanwhile, is still a question? Business gurus have seen environmentalism as a fringe topic since its emphasis on conservation and the acknowledgment of limits conflicts with the traditional marketing tenets of giving people what they want and selling as much as you can. Evidence suggests that by abiding by these three fundamental rules, effective green products have avoided green marketing myopia:

- A. *Consumer Value Positioning:*
 - Create environmental goods that are as good as (or better than) the competition.
 - Promote and offer the intended value of environmental products to consumers while focusing on key consumer market groups.
 - Bundle consumer wanted value with environmental products to broaden mainstream appeal.
- B. *Calibration of Consumer Knowledge:*
 - Educate customers with marketing messaging that relate environmental features with desired consumer value.
 - Describe environmental product qualities in terms of solutions for the demands of consumers
 - Create entertaining and instructional online site consumer's demand for eco items value.
- C. *Credibility of Product Claim:*
 - Make explicit and relevant environmental product and customer benefit claims.
 - Obtain product endorsements or eco certifications from reputable third parties, and inform customers about the significance of these endorsements and eco certifications.
 - Encourage customer evangelism by providing engaging, intriguing, and amusing information about

environmental products through consumers' social and online communication networks.

VII. CONCLUSION

The moment is ideal to choose "Green Marketing" internationally right now. If all nations adopt tight policies, it will bring about a significant change in the business sector since green marketing is crucial to preventing pollution. From a commercial standpoint, a skilled marketer is one who not only persuades customers but also actively includes them in the promotion of their goods. Green marketing includes an environmental and social component; therefore, it shouldn't be seen as just another marketing strategy. Instead, it needs to be pushed with much more zeal. Green marketing must become the rule rather than the exception or merely a fad given the grave threat posed by global warming. The safe and ecologically safe recycling of materials like paper, metals, and plastics has to be made much more widespread and systematized. The usage of energy-efficient lights and other electrical items has to become the standard. Marketers must also educate consumers about the advantages of green products over non-green ones and the reasons why they are necessary. Consumers are eager to spend more for a cleaner, greener environment, according to green marketing. Finally, pressure from consumers, business customers, and suppliers is needed to reduce harmful impacts on the environment. In emerging nations like India,

green marketing has an even greater significance and relevance.

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